

FIRST STUDY ON USING HEAVY TOW FIBERS FOR TEXTILE PREFORM PROCESSES IN THE AEROSPACE INDUSTRY

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ABSTRACT

In this study, a first investigation on the use of heavy tow carbon fibers for the aerospace industry is presented. With the constant pressure on cost and weight reduction, new ways for the future of carbon composite aircraft parts have to be explored. One idea is to use heavy tow fibers to reduce the costs of the baseline material and adapt the textile preform process chain to create efficient and competitive materials.

Since the ratio of carbon composites in commercial airplanes has reached its latest step of evolution with more than 50% structural weight in the Airbus A350 and Boeing B787, the expectations for new material systems are even higher than before. To compete with current state-of-the-art materials, new products and processes have to be investigated to reach the next level of high performance composites. One major drawback is the widely spread use of “black metal design” where the advantages of carbon fibers are still not fully explored.

The idea of this study was to conduct first tests to use heavy tow carbon fibers with a fiber titer of 50K or more in textile processes for structural parts of the aerospace industry. Currently available fibers were screened and three suitable fibers of different manufacturers were then selected. They were spread on a spreading machine to verify the usage in low areal weights which are needed for aircraft applications. One benefit of this could be the extension of current areal weights to a thin-ply material with less than 100 g/m². Therefore experiments are presented where the maximum spreading ratio and lowest areal weight of the fibers were conducted and the most influential parameters were examined. To assess the fiber damage and behaviour of the heavy tow carbon fibers panels were laid up with spread UD-tapes and infiltrated by using the VAP process. The coupons were then mechanically tested and the laminate was analysed in micro sections.

Further thoughts were made on the process chain and future steps to integrate heavy tow fibers in textile preform processes. These include the integration of additional multifunctional materials as well as processing to different widths for all kinds of textile preform processes.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the last 20 years, the aircraft market has changed from a purely performance driven to a more and more cost competitive market. The newest aircrafts of both of the two world leading aircraft manufacturers, the Boeing 787 and the Airbus A350, have a structural weight ratio of more than 50% Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastics and are targeted at long range flights, where every gram saves fuel. On the other hand, current developments aim at the short range market where the main criterion is cost reduction. Upgrades of the A320 and B737 family like the NEO-program are sufficient to satisfy the needs of the carriers to reduce fuel consumption for now. But new competitors like the Bombardier CS-series, the Sukhoi Superjet or the Chinese C919 are entering into a market, which is forecast at 20 to 25.000 single-aisle airplanes in the next 20 years ([1], [2]). These numbers show that the competition could be decided in costs and it will be hard for current production and manufacturing processes of Carbon Composites to compete against its rivals. The short range aircrafts with short flight durations and quick turnaround cycles with many load and unload cycles present a lot of challenges to the structure but nevertheless, they would always benefit from a lower structural weight.

The aim of this study was to have a first look on heavy tow fibers as a cost reducing alternative to the standard aerospace fiber materials, which are used nowadays. With an automotive industry that pushes the boundaries of production cycle times and material costs, the cost-intensive aerospace industry could benefit from new developments and accept the challenge to find new solutions to make flying cheaper, but also more eco-friendly. The main task is not only to use a less expensive fiber material but to find the right way between the highly automated processes of the automotive industry and the often-handmade structures in the aircraft production. With a monthly production number of less than 100 aircrafts, expensive technologies are hard to justify if they do not promise to improve performance and costs enough to minimize the risk of a new process. Especially in the composite market, processes depend on many variables and the material performance can vary on these parameters a lot. Automation and especially textile technologies are therefore niche processes but they still promise higher volumes and a reduction of energy-intensive autoclave cycles.

Considering these thoughts, this paper presents some results on the performance of current heavy tow fibers and investigations on the process from the dry fiber material to the finished part. The idea was to analyse the properties of three different commercial heavy tow fibers and compare them to a standard 12K aerospace fiber. A main parameter of a carbon fiber laminate is its layer thickness and the areal weight of the fiber material. When using fibers of a different titer the aspect ratio of the fiber cross section has to be adapted to achieve the predetermined thickness. Since heavy tow fibers are defined by having more filaments in one roving the low areal weights of the aerospace industry can only be achieved by spreading the fiber. By using very low areal weights one could maybe compensate the slightly lower mechanical performance and make use of thin-ply effects. The overall goal is to develop adapted preform technologies and use these fibers in textile and Out-of-Autoclave processes.

2 THEORY

2.1 Literature

Heavy Tow Fibers

The carbon fiber market is constantly growing and the theoretical worldwide production capacity was at about 100.000 tons in the year 2014 [3] with a demand of 50.000 tons of carbon fibers. Aside from the big part of the aerospace industry with one third of the global fiber demand and more than 50 percent of its turnover, heavy tows are currently catching up and dominate the wind and automotive market. With these two big domains, heavy tow fibers made about one third of the fiber production volume in 2012 [4]. And while the aerospace industry is already on a very high level of carbon fiber material share the wind and automotive market are on the very beginning. Growth rates of the CF demand are predicted to exceed 10 percent per year and carbon fibers are the enablers for new developments that help to enhance lightweight structures and reduce carbon emissions in both industries ([3]–[5]).

Currently, the biggest volume market for heavy tow carbon fibers is the wind industry. Several studies looked into the use of carbon fibers in wind turbines ([4], [6], [7]). In comparison to the normally used glass fibers, carbon fibers can allow for longer blades but are also much more expensive. Therefore, hybrid blade constructions are widespread and the market is hard-fought in regard to material prices. Further industries include the automotive ([8],[9]) and especially the sports industry, where carbon fibers are used for a long time and heavy tow fibers are a standard material ([10]).

In the aerospace industry, not many investigations were made to assess the possibilities of heavy tow fibers for structural parts. Early studies like the one from Cinquin et al. [11] stated that the fibers cannot reach the demanded mechanical performance, which is needed for aerospace applications. But with the challenges of today of reducing not only weight, but primarily costs of new aircrafts, heavy tow fibers could get another chance and are currently investigated to review their potentials.

Spreading

As already stated in chapter 1, the heavy tow fibers have to be spread to reach the areal weights that can be used in the aerospace industry. There are several ways to spread fibers, most of them are described in various patents and studies. The goal is always to rearrange the filaments so that the roving becomes wider than on the spool. The study of Irfan et al ([12]) gives an overview over some of the patents and techniques that are used for spreading. The methods can be distinguished in active, passive or a combination of both. Active methods use energy to spread the roving for example with an airflow (pressure or suction) ([13],[14],[15]) or by using (ultra-)sonic waves ([16], [17]) or vibrating elements for excitation. Passive methods include deflections beams ([12], [18]), convex ([19], [20],[21]) or other guiding elements ([22]) over which the roving is pulled.

Thin-Ply Composites

Because one idea of this study was also to spread the fibers to a very low areal weight, some literature is given to the topic of thin-ply composites. While the idea of spreading a roving has been present for a long time, some new findings were made regarding thin carbon fibers layer with an areal weight lower than 100 g/m². The origin of these developments can be found in Japan, where a team of scientists from Fukui university invented a new spreading method ([17]) and published their first studies on the effect in 2004 ([23]). After some further studies in Japan ([24], [25],[26]) a first international publication with the results was done in 2007 ([27],[28],[29]). In this study, Sihn et al. showed a significantly enhanced mechanical performance for thin-ply composites due to a better homogeneity of the material. The damage behaviour of cross-ply laminates changes from delamination in single layers to a brittle failure of the specimen which results in a better strength performance and better prediction of failure. Also other values like the fatigue and micro cracking behaviour could be dramatically enhanced. Until today, many studies have been conducted to assess the different effects of thin ply composites, for example to deepen the knowledge of fatigue specimen ([30]), the damage development ([31]) and the impact behaviour ([32]). Newer studies also looked at the thin-ply effects in non crimped fabrics, where similar results could be detected ([33], [34], [35]). Finally, also theoretical calculations and simulations were done to analyse thin-ply composites ([25], [36], [36], [37], [38]).

2.2 Calculations

In the beginning of the study, theoretical calculations of the aspect ratio of a carbon fiber roving were made. These help to compare the spreading behaviour of the different linear mass densities of the fibers. Table 1 shows the aspect ratio of the three standard areal weights from Airbus: low, medium and high grade plus one lower weight at 75 g/m² calculated for four linear fiber mass densities from 400 to 3200 tex.

Table 1: Aspect ratio of carbon fiber rovings - example calculation

Titer [tex]	Areal weight [g/m ²]			
	Low grade	Medium grade	High grade	
	75	134	196	268
400	69	22	10	5
800	138	43	20	11
1600	277	87	41	22
3200	554	173	81	43

The aspect ratio was calculated with formula (1) with t being the needed layer thickness (see formula (2)) of the areal weight and w the width of one carbon fiber roving at 100 percent of coverage (see formula (3)).

$$\text{aspect ratio} = \frac{w}{t} \text{ using:} \quad (1)$$

$$t = \frac{FAW \left[\frac{g}{m^2} \right]}{\rho \left[\frac{g}{m^3} \right] * FVC} \quad (2)$$

$$w = \frac{\text{titer [tex]}}{FAW \left[\frac{g}{m^2} \right]} \quad (3)$$

Figure 1 shows a diagram of the aspect ratio of the carbon fiber rovings for four different linear mass densities.

Figure 1: Aspect ratio of roving over FAW for different linear mass densities

Every fiber has a value of maximum spreadability, which can also be represented by the aspect ratio. The maximum value can only be determined in experiments and should be at the width where the fiber starts to get visibly damaged or inhomogeneous. In this study, some first experiments were made to assess the maximum ratio values of heavy tow fibers with about 3200 tex.

3 EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

3.1 Materials

The used fibers are listed in Table 2. All three heavy tow fibers are commercially available and should represent the state-of-the-art of this type of material. The standard fiber served as comparison and is already being used in structural aircraft parts. The mechanical performance of all of the fibers is at almost the same value of modulus and roughly at the same high tenacity fiber strength level. The laminates were preformed with an epoxy powder binder from Momentive (EPR 5311) and infused with the standard epoxy resin Hexcel RTM6 for infusion applications.

Table 2: Carbon fibers used in this study

Fiber type	Titer [tex]	Strength [MPa]	Modulus [GPa]	Density [g/cm ³]	Size content [% by mass]	Elongation [%]
<i>HT1</i>	3200	4830	250	1,81	1,0	1,9
<i>HT2</i>	3300	4000	240	1,80	1,0	1,7
<i>HT3</i>	3700	4100	240	1,80	1,5	1,6
<i>ST</i>	800	4300	240	1,77	1,0	1,8

3.2 Process

3.2.1 Spreading

The fibers were spread on a spreading machine LIBA UD500 which works with deflection and vibrating beams. Two different areal weights were configured to assess the processability and mechanical performance of the heavy tow fibers at a higher and a lower thickness. The areal weights 125 g/m² and 250 g/m² similar to the low and high grade material used for structural parts at Airbus (see Table 1 for areal weights) were selected. Since the number of tows was predetermined by the machine configuration the resulting areal weights differed due to the three slightly different tex values of the fibers. The final areal weight of each configuration was measured by weighing the preforms before the infiltration and used to calculate the normalized mechanical values.

Additional to these two values a third areal weight was tested to verify the spreadability and the lowest thickness that can be achieved with the machine for each fiber. In this testing setup, only one single roving was spread and then wound on a spool. The areal weight was measured manually via the tape width on several positions of the tape.

3.2.2 Specimen Preparation

The spread fiber tapes with a width of 250 mm were laid up by hand, preformed with a heating device and infiltrated using the Vacuum Assisted Process (VAP). Therefore, the dry preforms were put on a table and evacuated in a vacuum bag at 0 bars. Then the preform was heated up to 100°C and infused with preheated epoxy resin. After the calculated mass of resin was in the panel and the resin mass flow was below 0,5 g/min, a pressure difference of -350 mbar was set up to adjust the fiber volume content to the target of 60%. The used curing cycle was the standard cycle for 180°C-curing with a heating and cool-down rate of 2,5° C/min.

The cured panels were cut into the desired size with a water-cooled circular saw. Then the glass fiber tabs were applied on both sides with a 3M AF163 adhesive film material in a heated press. After the standard adhesion cycle at 100°C the panels were cut to the test specimen size and prepared for testing.

3.2.3 Visual inspection of specimen

The laminates were visually inspected via microsections which were examined on a reflected light microscope (Keyence VHX 2000 with lenses Z100 and Z1000). To characterize the fiber undulation of the materials, a minimum of 5 areas of every laminate were investigated. With this methodology the fiber undulation angles are measured and a statistical distribution of the angles can be calculated.

3.2.4 Mechanical Testing

The goal of this study was to assess the basic properties of heavy tow fibers in comparison to standard tows. Therefore, only the two basic mechanical test methods tension and compression were conducted. Tension testing is very sensitive and can visualize the fiber damage which is evoked in the spreading process. The compression specimens are more prone to fiber ondulation which could be caused by the combination of several rovings in a UD tape and even intensified in a 0/90 layup. Since the possibility of errors is quite critical in 0°-specimen, the 0/90° panels were also used for some of the tension specimen to verify the findings.

Tension tests were performed according to the ISO 527 and elongation was measured with an extensometer (MTS 634.31F-25). Compression tests were performed according to the DIN EN 2850 without strain gauges. For every test configuration, a minimum of 5 specimens were tested. All results were normalized to 60% fiber volume fraction.

4 RESULTS

4.1 Spreading

In this chapter some first results of the spreading process are shown. Since many of the parameters of the used spreading machine were fixed to reduce the variability in this study, a more detailed study is planned to assess the behaviour of the heavy tow fibers.

Figure 2: Spreading behaviour of heavy tow fibers

The diagram in Figure 2 shows the aspect ratio of the different fibers at a speed of 6 m/min and using a lower (50g) and a higher fiber tension (100g) which was adjusted at the creel. The ratios can be compared to the calculated values in chapter 2.2. The immersion depth is adjusted on the machine and results in a deflection angle of the fiber, both of these values are shown on the x-axis of the diagram. One can see that the behaviour of the different fibers was quite different. The fiber HT2 had a maximum aspect ratio of more than 1000, which would result in an areal weight of about 60 g/m².

In comparison to the standard fiber, the heavy tows had a much higher spreadability. At the deflection angle 0° and therefore a nearly out-of-the-box state of the roving, the difference between the aspect ratio of the standard and heavy tows stretched from 30 (HT1 at low tension) to 110 (HT2 at low tension). At higher deflection angles it became even bigger with a maximum difference of aspect ratio of 750 (HT2 at high tension).

The diagram in Figure 3 shows the fiber aspect ratio for different machine speeds and the three heavy tow fibers at a constant tension of 100g and a deflection angle of 30° on every spreading bar. It can be seen, that higher machine speeds resulted in a lower aspect ratio and therefore a higher areal

weight of the fiber. But since the differences were quite low, it was stated that the machine speed is not a limiting factor in the process chain of heavy tow carbon fibers. Some further parameters were also tested, but will be presented in a future publication.

Figure 3: Aspect ratio over machine speed

4.2 Material quality

Figure 4: Ondulation angles of laminates with 0,25/0,75 boxes and 0,01/0,99 error bars

The diagram in Figure 4 shows a boxplot chart with a box from the lower quarter (25%) to the upper quarter (75%) of the measured angles and error bars for 1% and 99% plus crosses for the values that are below 1% and above 99%. The analysis of the microsections showed that the fiber undulation angles of some of the heavy tow fibers were higher than of the standard tows. The three heavy tow fibers had a very different behaviour regarding undulation angles. While at HT1 the angles for lower and higher areal weights were quite similar, the angles at HT2 differed significantly. HT3 showed the expected values with lower maximum undulation angles at a lower areal weight due to a better homogeneity while the mean value was slightly higher.

4.3 Mechanical performance

In this section the results of the mechanical tests are presented. To compare the values between different fibers only relative values are given in the following diagrams. The relative value is the result of the mechanical testing results divided by the material property that was given in the fiber certificate of the commercial fibers.

Figure 5: Relative tension strength (left) and stiffness (right) of 0° UD specimen

Figure 5 shows the results of the tension tests of 2 mm UD-panels in 0°-direction. The values for the strength showed a significant relative difference of about 15 percent between the standard and the heavy tow fiber HT2 at the same areal weight of 125 g/m².

Regarding the calculations in chapter 2.2 the values should be compared at the same aspect ratio. As can be seen in Table 1, the ratio of a 800 tex standard fiber at 134 g/m² and a 3200 tex heavy tow fiber at 268 g/m² is nearly the same. So looking at the performance of the 125 g/m² ST versus the 250 g/m² HT is more comparable and the differences are smaller than 10% in relative tension strength. In contrast to the strength results, the values of the stiffness testing of ST and HT fibers were in a much smaller range. Due to the calculation of relative values, also values bigger than 1,0 are possible, which means that the results are slightly higher than calculated for a 60% (FVC) laminate.

For the fiber types HT1 and HT3, the difference between higher and lower areal weight was quite significant in both strength and stiffness while the material HT2 had no visible difference between the two areal weights.

Figure 6: Relative tension strength (left) and stiffness (right) of 0/90° specimen

The trends of the 0° tension specimen could be validated in the 0/90-testing shown in Figure 6. HT1 and HT3 seemed to have a difference in the material quality between lower and higher areal weight while HT2 stayed on the same level. Looking at the three fibers compared to each other, especially the strength values for HT1 were a little better than the others in 0/90-testing.

Figure 7: Relative compression strength of 0/90 specimen

Finally the compression test results in Figure 7 were on the same relative level for standard and heavy tow fibers except the slightly weaker fiber HT2. HT1 and HT2 did not show significant effects for lower versus higher areal weight, while the material HT3 showed the same trend as before at the tension tests. The standard tow fiber was a little better at lower areal weight, which could be explained by the constriction of the thin rovings in a relatively high areal weight.

5 DISCUSSION

The first spreading results showed that the heavy tow fibers have the potential to achieve quite low areal weights and are much more spreadable than the tested standard fibers, so that the areal weights that are used today are not an issue for heavy tows. The variation of the machine speed was an important parameter to validate the productivity but many other effects have to be investigated in a future study.

Looking at the mechanical performance, some of the results are quite promising and heavy tows seem to keep up with standard tows. The microsection investigations on the material quality showed that a lower areal weight does not always lead to a better homogeneity and lower ondulation angles. The results differed from the expected tendencies in the compression testing and indicate that other influences do also affect the properties of the laminate. One of them is the fiber damage that can lead to a lower tension value at 0° and could be the reason for the partly lower results of the 125 g/m² laminates of the three heavy tow fibers against the 250 g/m² material.

The HT2 fiber showed a very good spreading behavior which could be the reason for the equal results of mechanics for both areal weights. On the other hand the high ondulation angles did not show any influence on the compression and 0/90 test result which would have been expected. This example illustrates the difficult coherences and the need for further studies on the spreading process.

6 CONCLUSIONS

As this study was a first investigation in the area of heavy tow carbon fibers, besides first results it also raised some issues. Especially the experiments of the spreading process showed that a lot of parameters have an influence on the material. Since the aim of this study was to show the feasibility of the use of heavy tow fibers for aerospace applications, most of the spreading parameters were fixed. Further studies will investigate the material behavior at different machine parameters and also different spreading mechanisms.

The mechanical performance of the material was quite good compared to the standard fibers, but the results at low areal weights have to be analyzed in detail. It would also be interesting to see how the mechanical performance of the areal weights at the maximum aspect ratio compares to these findings. Therefore, the rovings have to be spread individually and then combined to build a tape or a panel.

Nevertheless, the results of this first investigation of heavy tow fibers for aerospace applications are very promising and the work will be continued to investigate further aspect of the topic.

REFERENCES

- [1] Airbus, “Airbus Global Market Forecast 2014-2033,” 2014.
- [2] Boeing, “Boeing: Current Market Outlook 2014-2033,” 2014.
- [3] T. Kraus and M. Kühnel, “Composites-Marktbericht 2014,” 2014.
- [4] M. Outlook, “Market Outlook : Surplus in carbon fiber’s future?,” pp. 1–6, 2015.
- [5] S. Black, “Gathering Momentum,” *Composites World*, 2012. .
- [6] P. Brøndsted, H. Lilholt, and A. Lystrup, “Composite Materials for Wind Power Turbine Blades,” *Annu. Rev. Mater. Res.*, vol. 35, no. 1, pp. 505–538, Aug. 2005.
- [7] D. A. Griffin, “Blade System Design Studies Volume I: Composite Technologies for Large Wind Turbine Blades,” 2002.
- [8] S. Das, “The cost of automotive polymer composites: a review and assessment of doe’s lightweight materials composites research,” 2001.
- [9] G. Rucks, J. Agenbroad, and S. Doig, “Kickstarting the widespread adoption of automotive carbon fiber composites.” Rocky Mountain Institute, 2013.
- [10] V. McConnel, “Large tow carbon fibre benefits sporting goods,” *Reinforced Plastics*, no. March, pp. 38–41, 1999.
- [11] J. Cinquin, “Aeronautical Composite Structure Cost Reduction from the Material Aspect,” in *Low Cost Composite Structures*, 2001, no. May.
- [12] M. S. Irfan, V. R. Machavaram, R. S. Mahendran, N. Shotton-Gale, C. F. Wait, M. A. Paget, M. Hudson, and G. F. Fernando, “Lateral spreading of a fiber bundle via mechanical means,” *J. Compos. Mater.*, vol. 46, no. 3, pp. 311–330, Nov. 2012.
- [13] J. C. Chen and C. G. Chao, “Numerical and Experimental Study of Internal Flow Field for a Carbon Fiber Tow Pneumatic Spreader,” vol. 32, no. April, pp. 329–339, 2001.
- [14] J. A. Newell and A. A. Puzianowski, “Development of a pneumatic spreading system for Kevlar-based SiC-precursor carbon fibre tows,” vol. 11, no. 1999, pp. 197–203, 2015.
- [15] K. Kawabe and S. Tomoda, “Multi-filament split-yarn sheet and method and device for the manufacture thereof,” 2000.
- [16] J. N. Hall, “Apparatus for spreading a graphite fiber tow into a ribbon of graphite filaments,” 1972.
- [17] S. Iyer and L. T. Drzal, “Method and system for spreading a tow of fibers,” 1991.
- [18] J. Nestler, F. Vettermann, and D. Reuchsel, “Vorrichtung und Verfahren zum Ausbreiten eines Karbonfaserstrangs,” 2005.
- [19] R. Marissen, L. T. Van Der Drift, and J. Sterk, “Technology for rapid impregnation of fibre bundles with a molten thermoplastic polymer,” *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 60, no. 10, pp. 2029–2034, 2000.
- [20] N. Nakagawa and Y. Ohsora, “Fiber separator for producing fiber reinforced metallic or resin body,” 1990.
- [21] H. Oishibashi, “Fiber spreading apparatus,” 2005.
- [22] J. Temburg, “Vorrichtung an einer faserverarbeitenden, ein Streckwerk aufweisenden Textilmaschine zur Führung eines Faserverbandes,” 1997.

- [23] H. Sasayama, K. Kawabe, S. Tomoda, I. Ohsawa, K. Kageyama, and N. Ogata, "Effect of Lamina Thickness on First Ply Failure in Multidirectionally Laminated Composites," *Japan Soc. Compos. Mater. J.*, vol. 30, no. 4, pp. 142–148, 2004.
- [24] Y. Nishikawa, T. Miki, K. Okubo, T. Fujii, and K. Kawabe, "Fatigue Behaviour of Plain Woven CF / Epoxy Composites using Spread Tows (Effects of Tow Thickness on Crack Formation)," *Japan Soc. Mech. Eng. Proc. (A Guid.)*, vol. 71, pp. 72–77, 2005.
- [25] T. Yokozeki, T. Aoki, T. Ogasawara, and T. Ishikawa, "Effects of layup angle and ply thickness on matrix crack interaction in contiguous plies of composite laminates," *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, vol. 36, no. 9, pp. 1229–1235, Sep. 2005.
- [26] K. Kawabe, H. Sasayama, K. Kageyama, and N. Ogata, "Effect of Ply Thickness on Compressive Properties in Multidirectionally Laminated Composites," *Japan Soc. Compos. Mater. J.*, vol. 34, no. 5, pp. 173–181, 2008.
- [27] S. Sihm, R. Y. Kim, K. Kawabe, and S. W. Tsai, "Experimental studies of thin-ply laminated composites," *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 67, no. 6, pp. 996–1008, May 2007.
- [28] S. W. Tsai, S. Sihm, and R. Y. Kim, "Thin Ply Composites," in *Structures, Structural Dynamics & Materials Conference*, 2005, no. April, pp. 1–5.
- [29] S. W. Tsai, "Thin Ply Technology." JEC 2005 - Aeronautics Forum, 2005.
- [30] Y. Nishikawa, K. Okubo, T. Fujii, and K. Kawabe, "Fatigue crack constraint in plain-woven CFRP using newly-developed spread tows," *Int. J. Fatigue*, vol. 28, no. 10, pp. 1248–1253, Oct. 2006.
- [31] R. Y. Kim, S. Sihm, and S. L. Donaldson, "Effect of ply thickness on the damage development in composite laminates," 2006.
- [32] H. Saito, M. Morita, K. Kawabe, M. Kanasaki, H. Takeuchi, M. Tanaka, and I. Kimpara, "Effect of ply-thickness on impact damage morphology in CFRP laminates," *J. Reinf. Plast. Compos.*, vol. 30, no. 13, pp. 1097–1106, Aug. 2011.
- [33] A. Arteiro, G. Catalanotti, J. Xavier, and P. P. Camanho, "Notched response of non-crimp fabric thin-ply laminates," *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 79, no. null, pp. 97–114, Apr. 2013.
- [34] A. Arteiro, G. Catalanotti, J. Xavier, and P. P. Camanho, "Notched response of non-crimp fabric thin-ply laminates: Analysis methods," *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 88, pp. 165–171, Nov. 2013.
- [35] A. Arteiro, G. Catalanotti, J. Xavier, and P. P. Camanho, "Large damage capability of non-crimp fabric thin-ply laminates," *Compos. Part A Appl. Sci. Manuf.*, vol. 63, pp. 110–122, Aug. 2014.
- [36] T. Yokozeki, Y. Aoki, and T. Ogasawara, "Experimental characterization of strength and damage resistance properties of thin-ply carbon fiber/toughened epoxy laminates," *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 82, no. 3, pp. 382–389, Feb. 2008.
- [37] A. Arteiro, G. Catalanotti, A. R. Melro, P. Linde, and P. P. Camanho, "Micro-mechanical analysis of the in situ effect in polymer composite laminates," *Compos. Struct.*, vol. 116, pp. 827–840, 2014.
- [38] R. Amacher, J. Cugnoni, J. Botsis, L. Sorensen, W. Smith, and C. Dransfeld, "Thin ply composites: Experimental characterization and modeling of size-effects," *Compos. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 101, pp. 121–132, Sep. 2014.